

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference with abbreviation in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common – not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Prevention of lodging in rice plants during rapid generation advance

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The maintenance of high nitrogen levels at the seedling stage is imperative for hastening flowering time during rapid generation advance (RGA). Dense spacing is needed to accommodate large numbers of segregating plants during RGA. The high nitrogen level and dense spacing conditions cause the breeding materials to become tall and to lodge as early as 3 weeks after planting. This creates inconvenience in raising the materials. Some plants may die unless

some leaf pruning is done, additional support is provided, or a chemical is sprayed to prevent plant elongation.

The tests we conducted showed that pruning the plants at 15 cm above the ground 22 days after sowing prevented the plants from becoming too tall but did not significantly delay flowering.

During pruning, one could also inoculate the plants for bacterial blight by the clipping technique.

Premature lodging can also be minimized by spraying B995 at 4,000 ppm on 35-day-old seedlings. Plant height can be reduced by as much as 40%, depending on the variety or line.

Another way of preventing lodging in plants growing in the RGA carts is to provide metal posts at each corner. The posts should have holes for strings that can help support the plants. ■

Submergence-tolerance screening of rice during rapid generation advance

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In rainfed wetland rice culture, total submergence of the rice plant is common, especially just after transplanting. Varieties for this situation need submergence tolerance. It has been shown that varietal differences in submergence tolerance exist and that screening for the trait at the seedling stage is easy.

In rainfed wetland rice where photoperiod-sensitive varieties may be required, the breeding process is accelerated through rapid generation advance (RGA). A study investigated the possibility of screening for submergence tolerance during the RGA process crosses for rainfed wetland rice. The efficiency of two types of containers was also tested. Presoaked seeds of 9 susceptible and resistant varieties were

sown in vials (3.0 cm diam, 4.5 cm high) and in square pots (5.2 cm diam, 5.0 cm high). Each vial or pot contained a single plant, and was replicated three times. Plants were submerged 10 days after sowing for 7 days and percentage of survival of each variety was recorded 7 days after treatment.

The known submergence-tolerant varieties FR 13A, Thavalu 15314, Kurkaruppan, and Thavalu 15325 did not differ in survival ability in the two containers. Susceptible varieties like IR42, IR38, IR8 showed different results but equally poor survival. The mean survival percentage of all varieties is greater in vials than in square pots, but the difference is not statistically significant.

Thus, vials can be used instead of square pots in tests for submergence tolerance. The vials will save space, but the green pots have a larger volume of soil and provide larger panicles. If screening is at F₄, more seeds may be required and a larger container like the